

DrugProt papers submission step by step

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IMPORTANT: This tutorial is for the submission of the DrugProt Short technical systems description papers.

Steps:

1. Write your paper following the instructions on the BioCreative page:

<https://biocreative.bioinformatics.udel.edu/events/biocreative-vii/biocreative-vii-workshop/>

Max length: 4 pages

Some tips:

- Analyze the detailed granular results by relation type (as each relation type has a particular practical impact).
- If you submitted for the Large Scale Track, include information on the challenges you faced and solutions you came up with to adapt your system to a Large Scale scenario.

2. Access <https://easychair.org/conferences/?conf=bc7>

3. Introduce your EasyChair **user name and password** (you may need to create a user, if you do not have one) and click Log In.

If you submitted your predictions through EasyChair, you should see the following page.

Author

- [author](#)

4. Click on **author** and then on **New submission**

My Submissions for BC7

Using the submission author environment you can view or manage your submissions to BC7. You can make new submissions or update your previous submissions.

To **make a new submission** click on "New Submission".

To **view or update your existing submission** click on the corresponding "view" icon.

Additional information about submission to BC7 can be found at the [BC7 Web page](#).

Questions about submissions can be sent to the conference contact email arighi@dbi.udel.edu.

Please note that if you do nothing (not even click on the menu) for more than two hours, your session will expire and you will have to login again.

#	Authors	Title	Track	View	paper	Program
3	Antonio Miranda	bsc-tutorial-predictions-v1	Track 1			

5. Select Track 1-DrugProt:Text mining drug/chemical-protein interactions

Select a Track

Please select the track relevant for your submission and click "Continue".

- Track 1-DrugProt:Text mining drug/chemical-protein interactions
- Track 2-NLM-Chem Track: Full text Chemical Identification and Indexing in PubMed articles
- Track: * Track 3-Automatic extraction of medication names in tweets
- Track 4- COVID-19 text mining tool interactive demo
- Track 5- LitCovid track Multi-label topic classification for COVID-19 literature annotation

6. Fill in the Author information.

Author 1 ([click here to add yourself](#)) ([click here to add an associate](#))

First name†: * Antonio

Last name: * Miranda

Email: * antoniomiresc@gmail.com

Country/region: * Spain

Organization: * Barcelona Supercomputing Center

Web page:

corresponding author

7. Fill in the **TITLE** and **ABSTRACT** of your paper.

Title and Abstract

The title and the abstract should be entered as plain text, they should not contain HTML elements.

Title: * BSC at DrugProt Large Scale Track: the impact of ...

Abstract: *

This is an example abstract

8. Fill in the **keywords**.

Keywords: *

transformers
relation extraction
large-scale NLP

9. Upload the **PDF** file and click **SUBMIT**.

Files

Submissions. Upload your Submission. For proceedings publications submit PDF format file. For other purposes follow instructions for your track. Note that the file size limit is 50 MB per submission.

Choose File No file chosen

Ready?

If you filled out the form, press the 'Submit' button below. **Do not press the button twice: uploading may take time!**

Submit

Congratulations! You have submitted your predictions. You should see a page like this:

BC7 Submission 128

The submission has been saved!

Submission 128	
Title:	BSC at DrugProt Large Scale Track: the impact of ...
Paper:	(Oct 05, 10:49 GMT)
Track:	Track 1-DrugProt:Text mining drug/chemical-protein interactions
Author keywords:	transformers relation extraction large-scale NLP
Abstract:	This is an example abstract
Submitted:	Oct 05, 10:49 GMT
Last update:	Oct 05, 10:49 GMT

Authors						
first name	last name	email	country	affiliation	Web page	corresponding?
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